

The EN-TRACK project

Energy Efficiency Performance-Tracking Platform for
Benchmarking Savings and Investments in Buildings

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 885395

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The EN-TRACK project

Energy Efficiency Performance-Tracking Platform for
Benchmarking Savings and Investments in Buildings

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Introduction and Background

- Buildings consume 40% of the energy in Europe, and 75% of the building stock is energy inefficient.
- Renovating buildings for **energy efficiency is a key priority** in European climate strategy, requiring increased investments from the private sector.
- **Lack of statistical data** on actual energy and cost savings achieved by energy efficiency investments is a major challenge.

Challenges

- Lack of standard data description among different platforms and databases.
- The information at building owners is not always well organized.
- Building owners have little incentive to share data.

Objectives

- Combine data from multiple sources.
- Enable massive and continuous data gathering.
- Provide attractive services to engage building owners.
- Provide benchmarking and risk assessment data for investors & FIs.

Project Overview

- **Open-source big data platform** for massive data gathering, harmonization, analysis, and benchmarking of building energy performance and investments.
- **Put into practice in Catalonia and Bulgaria**, collected data from over 5,000 buildings and 3,000 energy efficiency measures.
- 36 Months H2020 project: **Starting in October 2020** to October 2023.
- 7 partners from 5 countries:

Platform data workflow overview

Buildings Performance services

Understanding your buildings portfolio's performance characteristics

Useful for: Building Owners, Portfolio Managers, Compliance Officers

Simple tracking: Energy use trend monitoring

Longitudinal benchmarking: Normalised Energy use comparison to a baseline period.

Cross-sectional benchmarking: Comparison of the building's performance with a group of similar buildings.

Relevant indicators

(EUI) Energy Use Intensity kWh/m²·yr

(ECI) Energy Cost Intensity €/m²·yr

(EEI) Energy Emissions Intensity CO₂/m²·yr

Energy Efficiency Measures indicators

Understanding the value & opportunity cost of energy efficiency measures

Useful for: Portfolio Managers, Financial Analysts, Investors, Investment Underwriters, Loan Officers & Analysts

Cross-sectional benchmarking with time dimension: Comparison of a building's or EEM's performance indicator with similar ones considering the time the indicator refer to.

Relevant indicators

(EUSI) Energy Use Saving Intensity kWh/m²·yr

(AC) Avoidance Cost €/kWh

(SP) Simple Payback years

(NPV) Net Present Value €

(IRR) Internal Rate of Return %

Platform data workflow overview

Services for Stakeholders

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Building Owners & Operators

Energy managers, Building Portfolio managers, Energy auditors, ESCOs...

One-Stop-shop solution

- Single place to collect all building related data.
- Monitor the building stock performance in time.
- M&V of projects.
- Benchmarking (energy consumption, efficiency projects performance, CO₂ emissions, investments).
- Recommendations & Decision support tools.

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Financial institutions

Underwriter: Bank analysts, Project assessors, Project officers...

EEM Benchmarking & risk assessment

- Benchmark and compare the financial performance of energy efficiency projects in buildings.
- Evaluate investment of projects considering specific building characteristics.
- Assess CO₂ emissions reductions related to investments.

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Policy makers

Policy officer in a gov. or international institution, local Energy environment departments...

Reporting and decision support

- Track energy performance of the building stock & EE investments.
- Track achievement of environmental targets.
- Data-driven support for development of energy efficiency programmes and Energy Transition plans.
- Infrastructure enabling the implementation of energy disclosure legislation.

Platform roadmap & status

Overall platform architecture implemented and tested

EN-TRACK Common Data Model developed (aligned to DEEP, BEDES & other data standards)

Data collection initiated with uploading and harmonising data from tens of data sources

Interoperability working ~ 650 projects already shared with DEEP

User Interface and service launch at pilot scale

October 2022

User testing, UX validation and UI improvements

Platform launch to overall public

June 2023

Thank you

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www.en-track.eu

[@en_trackh2020](https://twitter.com/en_trackh2020)

[EN-TRACK H2020](https://www.youtube.com/EN-TRACK_H2020)

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Any question?

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